

Rac-8

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-2-rac-10%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	89	Acq. Method Set:	10% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 160 2 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/23/2022 10:44:15 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:35:17 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.785	3284108	49.85	318831
2	7.284	3303752	50.15	310775

Asy-8

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-2-asy-10%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	91	Acq. Method Set:	10% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 160 2 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/24/2022 7:12:16 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:34:59 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.795	9772044	96.41	945989
2	7.301	363851	3.59	36810